

Studies in Silicic Acid Gels. Part II. The Hydrogen-ion Concentration and Cataphoresis of the Gel-forming Mixtures.

BY MATA PRASAD AND R. R. HATTIANGADI.

It has been shown by Prasad and Hattiangadi (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 653) that on mixing solutions of neutral ammonium acetate of various concentrations to the same solution of sodium silicate, the time of setting of the gels decreases as the concentration of ammonium acetate is increased; high concentrations give flocculent precipitates instead of gels. But with acidic ammonium acetate, as its concentration increases, the time of setting at first decreases, reaches a minimum and then begins to increase. It has also been shown that the time of setting of the gels is considerably delayed in moderately acidic and highly alkaline medium and that the gels formed in their respective presence differ from each other in transparency.

Such a behaviour of acidic ammonium acetate is similar to that of acids as has been observed by Fleming, Holmes, and Fells and Firth. According to Fleming (*Z. Physik*, 1902, 41, 427) the time of setting of the gel is governed by the catalytic effect of the H- and OH-ions; but Holmes (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1918, 22, 510) concluded from his investigations that the dehydrating influence of the non-ionised molecules of the acids mixed with sodium silicate solutions was an important factor in controlling the setting of the gels. Fells and Firth (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, 29, 241) are also of the opinion that the time of setting of the silicic acid gel is not mainly governed by the H-ion concentration of the mixture but is influenced by the catalytic effect of the non-ionised molecules of the acids.

An attempt has, therefore, been made to study the hydrogen ion concentrations of the gel-forming mixtures and as the peculiar behaviour of the acidic ammonium acetate is due to the presence of free acetic acid in it, acetic acid instead of acidic ammonium acetate has been used in all the mixtures. The nature of silicic acid

in the acidic and alkaline mixtures has also been determined and the results obtained have thrown considerable light on the mechanism of gelation.

The hydrogen-ion concentration and the time of setting of mixtures of sodium silicate and other acids have also been studied in order to obtain definite knowledge of the role played by the H- and OH-ions and to determine the nature of the influence of different ions on the gel-forming mixtures.

Determination of the p_H values of the gel-forming mixture.

Kruyt and Postma (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1925, **44**, 765) have studied the changes in the p_H values of the silicic acid sol during dialysis and have used the electrometric method for these measurements. In the present investigation the indicator method of measuring the p_H was employed. This method is more useful though not as accurate as the electrometric one, as the measurements can be made in a very short time. This is very necessary as the p_H of some of the mixtures changes very rapidly with time. Also some gels set in a few seconds and the latter method which involves the bubbling of hydrogen, cannot be used here as this process will disturb the gel formation (*cf.* Part I).

The sodium silicate used in this investigation was Na_2O , $2\cdot33\text{SiO}_2$. A solution of 4 per cent. silica content titrated with 0.57 *N*-acid. Pyrex glass test-tubes which were thoroughly cleaned and dried were used for keeping the standard tints as well as the reaction mixtures. The buffer solution was prepared from B. D. H. "Universal buffer solution" which has an initial p_H of 3.1 and varies with the addition of 0.2*N*-NaOH or 0.2*N*-HCl according to the formula,

$$\text{Final } p_H = 3.1 \pm 1.185V$$

where *V* is the volume of the acid or alkali added.

Sodium hydroxide solution was prepared from Merck's extra pure sticks by making a saturated solution of caustic soda in redistilled water in Pyrex glass flasks and keeping it for 48 hours to allow the carbonate formed to settle to the bottom. The clear supernatant liquid was pipetted out and was carefully standardised. Hydrochloric acid solutions were prepared from Merck's pure compound.

The indicators used were B. D. H. chemicals and their concentrations employed were as obtained from British Drug House, Ltd. Only those of them were utilised, which had been used by Clarke, Lubs and Sørensen and had been shown to be free from many abnormalities.

The approximate p_H values of the gel-forming mixtures were first determined by the use of the 'Universal Indicator' supplied by the British Drug House which has a p_H range of 3 to 10. For accurate determinations 5 c.c. of the sodium silicate solutions were mixed with 5 c.c. of an acid in a pyrex glass tube to which 0.1 c. c. of the required indicator is already added. The tint of this mixture was laterally compared with the standard tints against clean white porcelain tiles. The stop-watch was started simultaneously with the mixing and the time of setting of the gel was also recorded. The change in p_H with the progress of time, if any, was also measured in the same way. But in these cases the slow coagulation of silicic acid produced an increasing turbidity in the reaction mixture and it was difficult to obtain the exact colour match with the standards. Neither was it possible to precipitate barium sulphate in the standard tints as suggested by Clark ("Determination of Hydrogen Ions", p. 71) to overcome this difficulty add to make them correspond with the reaction mixtures as the turbidity of the latter varied with time. In these experiments, therefore, great accuracy is not claimed but the discretion used to differentiate the various p_H values could give reproducible results. Besides, the indicators used being alcoholic solutions of organic substances, another factor has been introduced, caused by the specific influence of the alcohol on the gel-forming mixtures.

The results obtained with acetic acid in the alkaline and acid mixtures are given in the following tables:—

TABLE I.
Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2=2\%$. Reaction acidic.

Strength of acetic acid.	p_H .	Time of setting.
0.36N	5.4	10½ hrs.
0.325N	5.5	5 .. 27 mins.
0.30N	5.2	1 hr. 2 ..

There is no appreciable change in the p_H values during or after gelation.

TABLE I a.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 2\%$. Reaction alkaline.

Strength of acetic acid.	p_{H} .	Time of setting.
0.285N	Initial p_{H} 7.2, changes rapidly to 7.4 in 10 mins. and then to 7.7.	39 mins.
0.275N	Initial p_{H} 7.9, in 15 mins. 8.2, after complete gelation colour deepens corresponding to 8.4 p_{H} .	75 mins.
0.25N	Initial p_{H} 8.6, changes rapidly to 9.35	About a week.

TABLE II.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 3\%$. Reaction acidic.

Strength of acetic acid.	p_{H} .	Time of setting.
0.525N	5.3	4 hrs. 5 mins.
0.487N	5.5	2 48
0.45N	6.1	0 55

There is no appreciable change in the p_{H} during or after gelation.

TABLE IIa

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 3\%$. Reaction alkaline.

Strength of acetic acid.	p_{H}	Time of setting.
0.412N	Initial $p_{\text{H}} = 7.2$, changes rapidly to 7.7.	7 mins.
0.4N	Initial $p_{\text{H}} = 7.55$, changes rapidly to 8.2.	10 ..
0.375N	Initial $p_{\text{H}} = 8.5$, rapidly changes to 8.8.	53 ..

TABLE III.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 4\%$. Reaction acidic.

Strength of acetic acid.	p_{H} .	Time of setting.
0.7N	5.3	2 hrs.
0.65N	5.68	58 mins.
0.6N	6.2	13 ..

TABLE IIIa.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 4\%$. Reaction alkaline.

Strength of acetic acid.	p_{H} .	Time of setting.
0.575N	7.1-7.2, after 24 hrs. 7.6	5½ mins.
0.55N	7.69, changes to 8.2, 8.8	3½
0.525N	8.2, rapidly changes to 8.8	4½
0.50N	8.6, rapidly changes to 9.3	9½

TABLES IV and IVa,*
Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2 = 5\%$.

	Initial p_{H} .	Time of setting.
<i>Acidic.</i>	5.4	68 mins.
	5.65	30 "
	6.2	8 "
	7.8	1½ "
	8.4	2 "
<i>Alkaline.</i>	9.8	5 "
	10	7½ "
	10.2	38 "
	10.4	8 hrs.
	10.6	10 "

It will be seen from the foregoing tables that the p_{H} of the mixtures changes with the change in concentrations of silica and

Fig. 1.

the acid. It will be further noted from Fig. 1 that the minimum time of setting does not occur at one particular p_{H} of the gel-form-

* In this table mixtures having a p_{H} of less than 7 i.e., which are acidic do not show any appreciable change in the p_{H} values during or after gelation. But those above $p_{\text{H}} = 7$ show considerable changes in the p_{H} values as observed in preceding cases.

ing mixtures but depends upon the concentration of silica and is higher, the greater is the silica content of the mixture.

The effect of hydrochloric and sulphuric acids on the p_H values and the time of setting mixtures was next studied and the results obtained have been compared with those of acetic acid in the following tables.

TABLE V.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2=4\%$.

p_H .	Time of set with acetic acid.	p_H .	Time of set with HCl.	p_H .	Time of set with H_2SO_4 .
5.3	2 hrs.	5.15	2 hrs.	5.6	35 mins.
5.58	53 mins.	5.6	24 mins.	5.7	21½ "
6.2	13 "	5.7	13½ "	5.75	14½ "
7.1	5½ "	6.2	5½ "	5.8	12 "
7.7	3½ "	7.8	1½ "	6.8	4 "
8.2	4½ "	8.4	6½ "	7.2	3½ "
8.6	9½ "	8.8	12½ "	7.9	2½ "
...	...	9.0	27 "	8.6	13 "
...	8.8	50 "

TABLE VI.

Concentration of $\text{SiO}_2=5\%$.

p_H .	Time of setting with acetic acid.	p_H .	Time of setting with HCl.
5.4	63 mins.	5.4	18½ mins.
5.65	30 "	5.52	14
6.2	8 "	5.6	10
7.8	1½ "	5.9	3 45 secs
8.4	2 "	6.2	2 45 "
9.8	5 "	7.4	1 5 "
10.2	38 "	7.95	0 50 "
10.4	3 hrs.	9.35	7 mins.

It appears from the above that for the same p_H , acetic, hydrochloric and sulphuric acids give different times of setting. This probably depends on the influence of the other ions in the mixture, namely, acetate, chloride and sulphate. It will be further seen that when the p_H is below 7, that is, the mixtures are acidic, hydrochloric acid gives a gel earlier than sulphuric acid which again gives it earlier than acetic. But when the p_H is above 7, that is, the mixtures are alkaline, sulphuric acid delays the time of setting more than acetic or hydrochloric acids as shown in the p_H -time of setting curves (Fig. 2).

FIG. 2.

p_H -time-of-set curves with 4% SiO_2
and HCl , H_2SO_4 , and CH_3COOH .

Cataphoresis of the gel-forming mixtures.

It has been shown by Billiter (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, **51**, 150) by cataphoretic experiments that the silicic acid sol is negatively charged in alkaline and feebly acidic solutions, and positively, at higher hydrogen ion concentrations. Lösenbeck (*Koll. Chem. Beihefte.*, 1922, **16**, 27) has measured the migration velocity of the silicic acid sol particles with different concentrations of hydrochloric acid and found that the particles were negatively charged at first, but the

charge decreased continuously with increasing amounts of the acid, reached the iso-electric point and then reversed until the positive charge carried by the particles was much greater than the original negative charge. Similar observations have been made by Perrin (*Compt. rend.*, 1903, 136, 1388) and Pauli (*Beitr. chem. Physiol. Path.*, 1906, 7, 531.) in the case of albumin sols.

Sodium silicate undergoes hydrolysis as

The addition of neutral or acidic ammonium acetate may either hasten the hydrolysis or actually take part as a component of the reaction,

The latter view is supported by the fact that a large amount of ammonia is evolved when the two solutions are mixed together and the gel on drying gives out needle-like crystals of sodium acetate. The silicic acid freshly formed is, according to Mylius and Groschuff (*Ber.*, 1906, 39, 116), in the crystalloidal state but rapidly becomes colloidal.

The nature of the charge on the silicic acid particles in these mixtures was determined by means of cataphoresis carried on in a U-tube. Mixtures selected from the alkaline and acid regions for this purpose, were those which took fairly long time to set. On passing a current, a slow movement of the particles was observed towards the anode in the alkaline mixtures and towards the cathode in the acidic ones for sometime, and then a gel was formed in the anode and cathode compartments respectively. As is well-known the migration velocity of the emulsoids is very slow, and gel formation occurs in the limbs of the U-tube due to the neutralisation of the charge.

The p_{H} values of these mixtures were also measured by the method already described and the results obtained are the following:—

TABLE VII.

Mixture.	p_{H} .	Charge.
0.45N acetic acid and 4% SiO_2	... 10.1	Negative.
0.5N " "	... 8.6	"
0.64N " "	... 5.7	Positive
0.7N " "	... 5.3	"
25% Am. acetate etc. "	... 5.5	"

It will be seen from the above table that the reversal of the charge takes place at a very early stage, *i.e.*, when the mixtures are even slightly acidic. Kruyt and Postma (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the silicic acid sol is discharged at a $p_H = 2.5$, and until then the addition of hydrochloric acid to the sol produced no change in the nature of the charge. The difference in the reversal of the charges in the two cases referred to above may be ascribed to the fact that the above mixtures are undialysed sols of silicic acid and thus differ from the pure sols which are negatively charged even at a $p_H = 4.5$.

Discussion of Results.

The experiments on the cataphoresis of the various mixtures and the movement of the particles towards the electrodes indicate definitely the existence of colloidal particles in these mixtures. These particles have further been shown to be positively and negatively charged in the acidic and alkaline media respectively.

It will be seen from the results given in these pages that the minimum time of setting of the gels does not occur at the p_H value = 7 (Fig. 1) but is always higher. The minimum point in Fig. 2 (Part I) does not therefore indicate that mixtures containing higher concentrations of ammonium acetate than represented by this point are acidic or that the colloidal particles in these mixtures are positively charged.

Recent work of Powis (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1914, 71, 179, 186; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 109, 734) on an emulsion of a hydrocarbon oil in water, and colloidal arsenious sulphide, indicates that there is a critical value of the contact potential, not necessarily zero (neutral point) at or below which coagulation takes place easily.

As the gel formation from the mixtures studied here probably takes place by the coagulation of the silicic acid sol formed in these mixtures, the time of setting may be expected to be minimum at the isoelectric point of the sol particles. Assuming that the zero P. D. on the particles is indicated by the neutrality ($p_H = 7$) of the gel-forming mixtures, it appears that the P. D. on the silicic acid sol, in mixtures setting in minimum time, is not reduced to zero, but the particles still possess some small negative contact potential. An idea of the critical value of the negative contact potential on the particles can be obtained by the magnitude of the

difference in the p_H values of the mixtures at the minimum and neutral points ($p_H=7$) and is shown in the following table:—

TABLE VIII.
Neutral point $p_H=7$.

Concentration of SiO_2	p_H at minimum time.	Difference.
2 %	7.2	0.2
4 %	7.69	0.69
5 %	7.8	0.8

It will be seen from the above table that the critical potential for a colloidal solution of the same substance depends upon its concentration.

Mukherjee, Chaudhury and Choudhuri (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 493) during their investigation of the rate of migration of sols have found that the rate of migration of sols of As_2S_3 , gold, and $\text{CuFe}(\text{CN})_6$ diminishes with dilution, *i.e.*, the density of charge decreases and the sols are rendered more unstable.

It will further be seen from Tables Ia to IVa that when the mixtures are alkaline, the p_H values increase during and after gelation. This suggests therefore that some change, probably the hydrolysis of some unchanged sodium silicate, is taking place even after the gel has set.

When the mixtures are acidic, there are no perceptible changes in the p_H values during or after gelation. It appears, therefore, that during gelation from acidic mixtures, probably, only the neutralisation of the positive charge by the anions present in the mixture is taking place. The behaviour of sulphuric acid in the latter mixtures is, however, not in conformity with the Schulze-Hardy law of the coagulation of colloids. Sulphuric acid having a divalent anion is expected to be a better coagulant of the positive sol than hydrochloric or acetic acid. But the reverse has been observed to be the case.

It appears from the above discussion that the time of setting of a gel depends mainly, besides other factors such as viscosity and interfacial tension, upon two factors: (i) the density of the charge on the colloid particles which again is controlled by the relative adsorption of negative and positive ions—may be H- and OH-ions by the particle; (ii) the effective concentration of the coagulating agent present in the mixtures.